

Submitted: 25. 03. 2020

Published: 10. 04. 2020

Chameleodactyly: New term to describe the unique arrangement of digits in chameleons (Reptilia: Chamaeleonidae)

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Key words: Chameleodactyly, chameleodactylous, chamaeleodactylia, chameleons, digit arrangement, neologism, zygodactyly

Chameleons are lizards of the family Chamaeleonidae that are well known for many special morphological and physiological adaptations, such as laterally flattened body, pyramidal head, lungs with extensive pulmonary sacks, prehensile tail, color change, independently movable protruding eyes and long extendable tongues. Another unique anatomical feature is the special arrangement of the digits. NECAS (1999), TOLLEY & HERREL (2014).

Until now, the term zygodactyly has been incorrectly applied to chameleons (NECAS 1999; ANDERSON 2014). The term zygodactyly is derived from the Greek expression “ζυγος” (zygos) = “even” and δακτυλος (dáktylos) = “finger”. It is an arrangement of digits in the four-fingered birds, with two digits facing forward (digits 2 and 3) and two backwards (digits 1 and 4). This arrangement is typical for arboreal bird species, particularly those that climb tree trunks, like some representatives of the orders Psittaciformes, Piciformes, Cuculiformes and Strigiformes.

Fig 1. Chameleodactyly in *Chamaeleo arabicus* MATSCHIE, 1893; Photo PETR NEČAS

Fig 1. Zygodactyly and chameleodactyly comparison. Drawing PETR NEČAS

The number of digits in chameleons is 5, not 4 like in zygodactylous birds. In chameleons, the digits are divided into medial(inner) and lateral (outer) bundles and not into the longitudinal cranial (forward) and caudal (backwards) pairs like in birds. The front limbs of the chameleon feature three medial and two lateral digits whereas the hind limbs feature two medial and three lateral digits. The individual digits in the bundle are grown together up to the last phalanx, wearing claw. They build a pincer-like distal part of limb, unique in chameleons amongst all vertebrates.

ANDERSON (2014) recognized the inconsistency in nomenclature surrounding chameleon digits but did not propose a solution at the time. As a result of discussion of the author with Chris Anderson, and Mark Scherz, Darren Naish, Raul Diaz (in litt.), it is therefore proposed that the term chameleodactyly (adj. chameleodactylous; Lat. chamaeleodactylia) is universally adopted to describe the unique arrangement of digits in chameleons.

Fig 2. Left fore-limb of *Trioceros jacksonii xantholophus* (EASON, FERGUSON & HEBRARD, 1988); Photo PETR NEČAS

Fig 3. Left hind-limb of *Chamaeleo calyptratus* DUMÉRIL & DUMÉRIL, 1851; Photo PETR NEČAS

LITERATURE

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